

Densities and Excess Volumes for Binary Mixtures of Ethyl Acetate with several Polar and Non-polar Solvents at Two Temperatures

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Manuscript received 13 November 1985, accepted 7 June 1986

Densities and excess volumes for ethyl acetate-cyclohexane, ethyl acetate-benzene, ethyl acetate+toluene, ethyl acetate+ethylbenzene, ethyl acetate+carbon tetrachloride and ethyl acetate+chloroform at 313.15 K and for ethyl acetate+*o*-xylene, ethyl acetate+*p*-xylene, ethyl acetate+*p*-dioxane and ethyl acetate+tetrahydrofuran at 303.15 and 313.15 K have been reported. Positive $(\partial V^E/\partial T)_p$ is observed for the systems ethyl acetate+toluene, +ethylbenzene, +*o*-xylene, +*p*-xylene, +carbon tetrachloride, +chloroform and +tetrahydrofuran, and negative for ethyl acetate+cyclohexane and +*p*-dioxane systems.

THE present work is a part of an investigation of molecular interactions between components of binary mixtures of esters with polar and non-polar solvents¹⁻³. Earlier, densities and excess volumes for binary mixtures of ethyl acetate+cyclohexane, +benzene, +toluene, +ethylbenzene, +carbon tetrachloride and +chloroform at 303.15 K have been reported^{1,2}. Here densities and excess volumes at 313.15 K for the above binary mixtures in addition to ethyl acetate+*o*-xylene, +*p*-xylene, +*p*-dioxane, and +tetrahydrofuran (THF) at 303.15 and 313.15 K are reported to calculate the temperature coefficient $(\partial V^E/\partial T)_p$.

Experimental

Ethyl acetate, benzene, *o*-xylene, *p*-xylene, *p*-dioxane and tetrahydrofuran were of AnalaR grade, cyclohexane and toluene were of S.R.L., AR grade, and carbon tetrachloride and chloroform were of B.D.H. spectroscopic grade. The reagents were further purified by standard procedures⁴. The details of procedures followed for purification of ethyl acetate, cyclohexane, benzene, toluene, carbon tetrachloride and chloroform are given in our earlier papers^{1,2}. The same procedure was followed for *o*-xylene and *p*-xylene as was for benzene purification. *p*-Dioxane was first refluxed with sodium hydroxide and then with sodium until free from peroxide and finally fractionally distilled over sodium. Tetrahydrofuran was refluxed with potassium hydroxide for several hours and finally distilled over sodium. Purity of purified liquids was checked by measuring refractive index and density at 303.15 K which agreed well with literature values^{4,5}. The apparatus and procedure for the measurement of density are described elsewhere⁶. The density data are correct to ± 0.0001 units. Mixtures were prepared by weighing the liquids in

ground stoppered weighing flasks taking due precautions to minimise evaporation.

Results and Discussion

The measurements of density were made at 303.15 and 313.15 K over entire range of composition for all the binary systems. The excess volumes V^E were calculated from the density data using relation (1)

$$V^E = (M_1X_1 + M_2X_2)/d_{12} - (M_1X_1/d_1 + M_2X_2/d_2) \quad (1)$$

where, M , X and d represent molecular weight, mole fraction and density, respectively. Subscripts 1, 2 and 12 refer to pure components and mixtures, respectively. The density and excess volume data are given in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—DENSITY (d) AND EXCESS VOLUME (V^E) FOR ETHYL ACETATE BINARY MIXTURES AT 303.15 K

X_1^*	d g cm ⁻³	V^E cm ³ mol ⁻¹
Ethyl acetate+ <i>o</i> -Xylene		
0.0	0.8717	—
0.0599	0.8727	-0.024
0.1789	0.8745	-0.034
0.2918	0.8763	-0.056
0.4303	0.8786	-0.064
0.4994	0.8798	-0.072
0.5537	0.8807	-0.070
0.6001	0.8814	-0.057
0.6951	0.8830	-0.046
0.7859	0.8846	-0.037
0.8730	0.8862	-0.028
0.9583	0.8878	-0.017
1.0	0.8885	—

(Table 1 contd.)

(Table 2 contd.)

Ethyl acetate + <i>p</i> -Dioxane		
0.0	1.022 3	—
0.045 1	1.015 6	-0.016
0.133 2	1.002 7	-0.044
0.177 9	0.996 2	-0.051
0.223 6	0.989 7	-0.063
0.318 7	0.976 3	-0.075
0.417 6	0.962 6	-0.075
0.467 0	0.955 8	-0.065
0.515 5	0.949 2	-0.053
0.618 2	0.935 6	-0.037
0.724 3	0.922 0	-0.025
0.829 7	0.908 9	-0.015
0.941 1	0.895 5	-0.011
1.0	0.888 5	—

Ethyl acetate + <i>p</i> -Xylene		
0.0	0.852 3	—
0.062 4	0.854 2	-0.011
0.132 8	0.857 9	-0.018
0.233 8	0.861 9	-0.026
0.403 1	0.865 6	-0.043
0.505 6	0.868 9	-0.046
0.552 0	0.870 7	-0.060
0.604 1	0.872 6	-0.056
0.697 6	0.876 1	-0.044
0.788 7	0.879 7	-0.037
0.875 7	0.883 2	-0.021
0.958 5	0.886 8	-0.019
1.0	0.888 5	—

Ethyl acetate + THF		
0.0	0.876 8	—
0.043 1	0.877 3	0.010
0.083 7	0.877 8	0.015
0.171 8	0.878 9	0.023
0.262 5	0.879 9	0.031
0.350 4	0.881 0	0.041
0.409 7	0.881 6	0.054
0.452 1	0.882 2	0.044
0.654 4	0.884 6	0.035
0.766 9	0.885 9	0.026
0.822 9	0.886 5	0.025
0.881 7	0.887 2	0.014
0.939 6	0.887 8	0.012
1.0	0.888 5	—

* Mole fraction of ethyl acetate.

TABLE 2—DENSITY (d) AND EXCESS VOLUME (V^E) FOR ETHYL ACETATE BINARY MIXTURES AT 313.5 K

X_1^*	d g cm ⁻³	V^E cm ³ mol ⁻¹
Ethyl acetate + Cyclohexane		
0.0	0.760 4	—
0.205 2	0.776 1	0.889
0.408 5	0.796 4	1.171
0.509 7	0.807 7	1.187
0.605 6	0.819 2	1.125
0.798 9	0.844 7	0.808
1.0	0.876 5	—
Ethyl acetate + Toluene		
0.0	0.848 5	—
0.208 0	0.854 1	-0.016
0.409 0	0.859 2	0.029
0.506 9	0.861 9	0.031
0.605 7	0.864 7	0.029
0.800 4	0.870 5	0.007

Ethyl acetate + <i>o</i> -Xylene		
0.0	0.863 2	—
0.205 6	0.865 6	-0.011
0.407 9	0.867 8	0.025
0.502 3	0.869 0	0.027
0.598 8	0.870 1	0.051
0.801 8	0.873 2	0.025

Ethyl acetate + Carbon tetrachloride		
0.0	1.555 3	—
0.205 9	1.412 7	0.072
0.404 6	1.276 7	0.101
0.503 3	1.209 6	0.108
0.601 4	1.143 1	0.116
0.800 8	1.009 3	0.066

Ethyl acetate + <i>p</i> -Dioxane		
0.0	1.011 1	—
0.209 0	0.980 1	-0.041
0.405 0	0.952 5	-0.059
0.514 4	0.937 9	-0.063
0.602 0	0.926 3	-0.078
0.799 4	0.901 2	-0.071

Ethyl acetate + Benzene		
0.0	0.857 4	—
0.208 3	0.861 0	0.075
0.404 8	0.864 7	0.097
0.501 6	0.866 5	0.105
0.601 0	0.868 5	0.092
0.802 8	0.872 5	0.059
1.0	0.876 5	—

Ethyl acetate + Ethyl benzene		
0.0	0.849 5	—
0.206 1	0.853 8	0.051
0.404 1	0.858 3	0.098
0.501 5	0.860 8	0.102
0.603 4	0.863 6	0.097
0.799 1	0.869 7	0.045

Ethyl acetate + <i>p</i> -Xylene		
0.0	0.843 6	—
0.206 3	0.849 3	-0.006
0.407 7	0.855 2	0.010
0.506 1	0.858 2	0.027
0.599 1	0.861 2	0.039
0.801 6	0.868 5	0.026

Ethyl acetate + Chloroform		
0.0	1.452 0	—
0.207 3	1.313 2	-0.041
0.403 5	1.191 3	0.014
0.500 3	1.134 9	0.029
0.601 2	1.078 6	0.027
0.803 4	1.972 3	0.018

Ethyl acetate + THF		
0.0	0.866 8	—
0.204 4	0.868 3	0.090
0.405 9	0.870 2	0.102
0.507 2	0.871 2	0.103
0.600 2	0.872 0	0.113
0.799 6	0.874 0	0.093

* Mole fraction of ethyl acetate.

The excess volumes, V^E were fitted to the empirical equation (2),

$$V^E = X_1 X_2 [a + b(1 - 2X_1) + c(1 - 2X_1)^2] \quad (2)$$

The values of the constants a , b and c are given in Table 3 along with the standard deviation σ

TABLE 3—VALUES OF CONSTANTS a , b AND c OF EQUATION (2) ALONGWITH STANDARD DEVIATION σ

Systems	Temp. K	a	b	c	σ
Ethyl acetate + <i>o</i> -Xylene	303.15	-0.284 1	-0.023 3	-0.168 9	0.009 5
Ethyl acetate + <i>p</i> -Xylene	303.15	-0.171 8	0.102 8	-0.119 6	0.009 1
Ethyl acetate + <i>p</i> -Dioxane	303.15	-0.235 6	-0.158 4	-0.044 2	0.007 7
Ethyl acetate + THF	303.15	0.166 5	0.020 8	0.034 4	0.005 2
Ethyl acetate + Cyclohexane	313.15	4.739 6	0.391 7	1.377 2	0.003 9
Ethyl acetate + Benzene	313.15	0.402 4	0.067 7	0.031 1	0.004 1
Ethyl acetate + Toluene	313.15	0.131 6	-0.115 7	-0.452 6	0.005 2
Ethyl acetate + Ethyl benzene	313.15	0.415 5	0.020 5	-0.398 2	0.002 0
Ethyl acetate + <i>o</i> -Xylene	313.15	0.145 4	-0.201 6	-0.280 6	0.009 4
Ethyl acetate + <i>p</i> -Xylene	313.15	0.105 4	-0.183 9	-0.122 7	0.006 3
Ethyl acetate + Carbon tetrachloride	313.15	0.445 8	0.003 3	-0.050 7	0.008 7
Ethyl acetate + Chloroform	313.15	0.105 9	-0.298 5	-0.504 0	0.007 8
Ethyl acetate + <i>p</i> -Dioxane	313.15	-0.296 4	0.167 5	-0.131 0	0.007 1
Ethyl acetate + THF	313.15	0.426 1	-0.076 2	0.312 3	0.004 0

TABLE 4—EXCESS VOLUME (V^E) AND TEMPERATURE COEFFICIENT $(\partial V^E/\partial T)_p$ AT $X_1 = X_2 = 0.5$

Systems	V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)		$(\sigma V^E)/(\sigma T)_p$ cm ³ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
	303.15 K	313.15 K	
Ethyl acetate + Cyclohexane	1.235	1.184	-0.003 9
Ethyl acetate + Benzene	0.104	0.106	0.000 2
Ethyl acetate + Toluene	-0.042	0.033	0.007 5
Ethyl acetate + Ethyl benzene	0.066	0.104	0.003 8
Ethyl acetate + <i>o</i> -Xylene	-0.058	0.036	0.009 4
Ethyl acetate + <i>p</i> -Xylene	-0.043	0.026	0.006 9
Ethyl acetate + Carbon tetrachloride	0.039	0.111	0.007 2
Ethyl acetate + Chloroform	-0.002	0.027	0.002 9
Ethyl acetate + <i>p</i> -Dioxane	-0.059	-0.074	-0.001 5
Ethyl acetate + Tetrahydrofuran	0.042	0.107	0.006 5

defined by equation (3),

$$\sigma^2 = \sum \{V_{\text{exp}}^E - V_{\text{cal}}^E\}^2 / (n-3) \quad (3)$$

where, n is the total number of measurements.

The excess volumes for mixtures ethyl acetate + *o*-xylene, ethyl acetate + *p*-xylene and ethyl acetate + *p*-dioxane are small negative at 303.15 K, while for ethyl acetate-tetrahydrofuran, they are small positive. It is observed that excess volume for the systems ethyl acetate + toluene, + ethylbenzene, + *o*-xylene, + *p*-xylene, + tetrahydrofuran, + carbon tetrachloride and + chloroform, increases with the increase in temperature, i.e. $(\partial V^E/\partial T)_p$ is positive whereas $(\partial V^E/\partial T)_p$ is negative for the ethyl acetate + cyclohexane and + *p*-dioxane systems. The excess volumes and temperature coefficient $(\partial V^E/\partial T)_p$ at $X_1 = X_2 = 0.5$ are given in Table 4.

Acknowledgement

Financial assistance from C.S.I.R., New Delhi, is gratefully acknowledged. Authors are thankful to Prof. H. B. Naik, Head, Department of Chemistry, for providing facilities and to Miss Palsanawala P.P. for helping in calculation of results.

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